

Lung-CABO: Lung Cancer Concepts Association Biological Ontology

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Abstract—Lung cancer is one of the deadliest types of cancer and poses a significant public health challenge. Despite numerous studies identifying various risk factors associated with this disease, further research remains essential, particularly in the biological domain. Currently, multiple data sources compile biological information on various diseases, including lung cancer and its subtypes. However, these sources often differ in structure and format, making data extraction and efficient use in artificial intelligence (AI) models more challenging. Ontologies, semantic technologies, and data reuse strategies play a crucial role in addressing this issue. By leveraging these approaches, it is possible to build a knowledge graph that integrates heterogeneous data sources into a unified format, facilitating interoperability and data extraction. Lung-CABO is an ontology specifically designed for lung cancer and its subtypes, whose effectiveness has been evaluated. Through this ontology, a knowledge graph has been developed to explore, extract, and utilize information both to identify risk factors and as input for AI models. Additionally, Lung-CABO is reusable and can be expanded by incorporating association classes that integrate other relevant data related to the disease, such as environmental factors, further enhancing its scope and applicability.

Index Terms—Lung cancer, Ontology, Semantic technologies, Knowledge Graph, biological ontology.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer remains one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide, representing a significant public health challenge. According to the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC, 2022), lung cancer ranks first in incidence (12.4%) and mortality (18.7%) among all cancers [1]. The most common types of lung cancer are non-small cell lung carcinoma (NSCLC) and small cell lung carcinoma (SCLC). NSCLC accounts for approximately 85%-90% of all lung cancer cases and includes three major subtypes: adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, and large cell carcinoma.

Among these, adenocarcinoma is the most prevalent, constituting around 40% of NSCLC cases. Squamous cell carcinoma represents about 25%-30%, and large cell carcinoma accounts for 10%-15% [2]. The second major type, small cell lung cancer (SCLC), accounts for approximately 13%-15% of all lung cancer cases [3]. SCLC is also the most aggressive and lethal subtype. It is classified as a neuroendocrine carcinoma, characterized by rapid proliferation and early metastasis [4].

Although significant progress has been made in medical research and early detection, lung cancer continues to have a high fatality rate. Late-stage diagnosis and the complexity of its risk factors remain major challenges in improving survival rates [5], [6].

Understanding the risk factors for lung cancer is particularly challenging, as they encompass biological, environmental, epidemiological, and lifestyle-related components. Smoking is widely recognized as the primary risk factor [7]–[9]. However, beyond tobacco exposure, various environmental factors significantly contribute to disease risk. These include physical agents such as ionizing radiation from radon and non-ionizing ultraviolet (UV) radiation, as well as chemical pollutants. Hazardous substances like asbestos, dioxins, and heavy metals (e.g., arsenic, chromium, nickel, and cobalt) are known carcinogens commonly found in industrial emissions, household pollutants, and second-hand smoke, all of which further increase the likelihood of lung cancer development [10].

From a biological perspective, genetic predisposition also plays a crucial role in an individual's likelihood of developing lung cancer. Mutations in tumor suppressor genes, particularly p53, can impair the body's ability to regulate cell growth and repair DNA damage, making cells more vulnerable to carcinogenic factors. Additionally, family history, high-penetrance

genes, and genetic polymorphisms have been associated with an increased risk of lung cancer. Recent genome-wide association studies have identified several genetic polymorphisms involved in lung cancer, highlighting inherited susceptibility to the disease [11]–[13].

Despite advances in research, many genetic and biological factors influencing susceptibility remain unclear [14]. Therefore, integrating diverse biological knowledge is essential to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of lung cancer development.

Efforts such as the LUCIA (Lung Cancer-related risk factors and their Impact Assessment) project, aligned with the EU Cancer Mission, aim to enhance research by identifying risk factors associated with lung cancer and its subtypes to improve early diagnosis strategies [15]. However, biological information is often scattered across multiple independent databases, making it difficult to obtain a unified view of disease mechanisms and risk assessment. This fragmentation highlights the need for structured knowledge frameworks capable of integrating, organizing, and analyzing large-scale biological data.

To address this challenge, we propose Lung-CABO (Lung Cancer Disease Biological Concepts Association Ontology), an ontology and knowledge graph specifically designed to integrate and structure lung cancer-related biological information. Unlike previous efforts, Lung-CABO focuses exclusively on biological data related to lung cancer, incorporating data from carefully curated public resources such as DISEASE [16], COSMIC [17], Mitelman [18], WikiPathways [19], and DisGeNET [20]. This ensures that the ontology offers a comprehensive and high-quality representation of lung cancer risk factors, with a particular emphasis on biological aspects.

Lung-CABO serves as a centralized and semantically rich knowledge graph, allowing researchers and clinicians to:

- Explore and exploit diverse biological datasets to identify relationships between lung cancer, genes, pathways, chromosomal abnormalities, gene fusions, and genetic variants.
- Identify lung cancer risk factors based on curated biological evidence.
- Support knowledge discovery and hypothesis generation through SPARQL queries and ontology-based visualizations.

The rest of the paper is organized in the following way: in Section II, the most relevant works on ontology creation are explored. Then, in Section III, the methodology followed to develop the ontology is explained. Section IV describes the ontology and its component modules. Later, in Section V, the ontology evaluation process is detailed. Finally, Section VI presents the conclusions and possible lines of future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Biological ontologies provide structured vocabularies that facilitate knowledge representation, data standardization, and semantic interoperability across different domains [21]. Numerous ontology-driven initiatives have emerged to model

diseases, capture genetic associations, standardize terminology, and integrate biological pathways. This section outlines representative ontologies grouped by their primary focus.

A. *Biological Ontology Frameworks and Repositories*

One of the most prominent initiatives in biological ontology development is the Open Biological Ontologies (OBO) Foundry [22], which is a collaborative initiative that promotes best practices and interoperability in ontology development, hosting over 60 ontologies spanning genomics, disease classification, and molecular biology. Complementing this, BioPortal [23] is an open repository that enables browsing, reuse, and mapping of concepts across a vast collection of biological ontologies.

Another fundamental ontology in this context is the Semantic Science Integrated Ontology (SIO) [24] that offers a high-level, flexible schema for representing biological entities and their relationships, serving as a bridge for integrating diverse biological datasets.

B. *Medical Terminologies and Disease Representation*

Standardized terminologies are essential for consistent biological data representation. The National Cancer Institute Thesaurus (NCIT) [25] offers controlled vocabularies for cancer-related concepts, including diseases, treatments, and biomarkers. At a broader level, the Unified Medical Language System (UMLS) [26] integrates multiple biomedical terminologies to support semantic interoperability across systems. Additionally, Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) [27] enable standardized indexing and retrieval of biomedical literature.

C. *Disease and biological Associations Ontologies*

Several ontologies focus on linking diseases with genetic and biological data. The Disease Ontology (DO) [28] provides a hierarchical classification of human diseases, integrating clinical and genetic information. DisGeNET [20] aggregates gene-disease associations from curated databases, experimental data, and literature. SEM-DISNET [29] expands this by linking diseases, genes, drugs, and pathways through semantic web technologies.

For genetic variation modeling, the Genotype Ontology (GENO) [30] standardizes descriptions of genetic and allelic variation, supporting integration of genotype-phenotype data.

Finally, understanding biological pathways is essential for modeling disease mechanisms, drug interactions, and metabolic processes. WikiPathways [19] is a community-driven knowledge platform dedicated to the curation and dissemination of biological pathways. By providing structured representations of signaling and metabolic pathways, WikiPathways enables researchers to study molecular interactions and disease-related perturbations in biological networks.

Lung-CABO was designed to address gaps in existing ontologies by integrating multiple biological aspects of lung cancer into a unified knowledge graph. It brings together gene-disease associations, genetic variants, chromosomal abnormalities, gene fusions, and relevant metabolic pathways

into a single, structured framework. Unlike broader or domain-generic resources, Lung-CABO provides a focused and semantically enriched representation of lung cancer biology. Its extensible architecture also allows for the future incorporation of other relevant lung cancer-related data, positioning it as a comprehensive and adaptable tool to support biomedical research and computational analysis in this domain.

III. METHODOLOGY

The Lung-CABO ontology was developed following the Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology. LOT is a lightweight methodology focused on the reuse of existing terms in already published vocabularies or ontologies and on the publication of the ontology following Linked Data principles [31]. LOT is based on the NeOn methodology [32]. The workflow consists of four activities: Ontological requirements specification, Ontology implementation, Ontology publication, and Ontology maintenance. The following is an overview of the activities and their role in the development of Lung-CABO.

A. Ontological requirements specification

The first activity is to determine the purpose and boundaries of the ontology, clearly defining what aspects it will cover and for what purpose. In addition, it is essential to identify the requirements it must meet to ensure that it responds to the needs of the project effectively. The ontology requirements can be found through the portal¹ [31].

B. Ontology implementation

The main objective of this activity is to generate the ontology using a formal language, considering the requirements described in the previous activity, taking into account that this will be refined in the development. The conceptualization is where the ontology is represented graphically and where the classes, hierarchies and relationships are identified. For the conceptualization, the Cholk notation [33] was followed and implemented using the Ontology Web Language (OWL 2) [34], and built with Protégé editor [35]. The evaluation was performed using Ontology Pitfall Scanner! (OOPS!) [36] to identify errors in the TBOX modeling and with SPARQL queries.

C. Ontology publication

In the publication activity, the ontology is prepared with its respective documentation. A Wizard for Documenting Ontologies (Widoco) [37] was used to generate the documentation. Although the ontology has not been officially published yet, the related documentation is available in the following GitHub repository².

D. Ontology maintenance

The last activity consists of keeping the ontology updated and available for new requirements through GitHub.

IV. ONTOLOGY DESCRIPTION

Lung-CABO is an ontology designed to integrate and structure biological information related to lung cancer. The ontology integrates curated data from multiple public biological resources, selected based on their relevance to lung cancer biology. Key variables were extracted from each source to ensure a structured and semantically rich representation.

- DISEASE [16]: an integrative resource of disease–gene associations, combining text mining with curated databases, cancer mutation data, and genome-wide association studies (GWAS). It features an efficient dictionary-based entity recognition system and a co-occurrence scoring approach to extract associations from the biological literature. Extracted variables: diseases, associated genes, co-occurrence and ranking scores (Z-score, Mean Rank Score, Co-occurrence Score), literature references.
- COSMIC [17]: a key resource for somatic mutations, essential for modeling genetic alterations in lung cancer. Extracted variables: diseases, genes, variants, chromosomes, chromosomal positions (start-end), reference and alternative alleles, literature references.
- Mitelman Database [18]: focused on chromosomal abnormalities and gene fusion, crucial for representing structural variations and relevant genes in lung cancer. Extracted variables: disease, chromosomal abnormalities, gene fusions, literature references.
- WikiPathways [19]: a repository of biological pathways. Extracted variables: Pathways associated with lung cancer-related genes and diseases, gene products, and metabolites.
- DisGeNET [20]: a large-scale database of gene-disease associations (GDAs), widely used for biological research. Extracted variables: Diseases, associated genes, evidence indicators (Evidence Index, Evidence Level, Score), gene-specific properties (Disease Specificity, Disease Pleiotropy, Probability of Being Loss-of-Function Intolerant), literature references.

The proposed ontology is built upon the reuse of existing ontologies, ensuring that their concepts align with the defined entities. Its design is based on the structure of the DisGeNET ontology, which models associations between diseases, genes, and variants. The ontology comprises 41 classes and 17 object properties, with 35 classes and 16 object properties adapted from established vocabularies such as SIO, NCI, OBO, Wikipathways, GENO, and MeSH. The remaining elements were specifically developed for Lung-CABO.

In the Lung-CABO ontology, the core entity are diseases, represented by the class *Disease, Disorder or Finding* `ncit:C7057`, which enables a standardized representation of lung cancer. The organism in which the disease occurs is described by `ncit:C1450`, while its semantic type is captured by `ncit:C43817`.

¹<https://deliaamintamoreno.github.io/LungCABO-Resources/>

²<https://github.com/deliaamintamoreno/LungCABO-Resources>

Fig. 1. Representation of the Lung-CABO schema.

A. Disease-Pathway Association

This relationship is modeled through `CABO:PathwayDiseaseAssociation`. The class `CABO:Pathway` represents the metabolic pathway associated with the disease and is linked to `wp:Metabolite` (metabolites) and `wp:GeneProduct` (gene products).

B. Disease-Gene Association

This association is represented by `sio:SIO_00098` and includes various indicators such as `Score` (`ncit:C25338`), `Z-score` (`ncit:C68741`), and `Evidence Level` (`ncit:C15639`). Lung-CABO also includes specific metrics like `EvidenceIndex`, `cooccurrenceScore`, and `meanRankScore`.

Genomic biomarkers within this association include `Chromosomal Rearrangement` (`sio:SIO_001349`), `Gene Fusion` (`sio:SIO_001348`), and `Susceptibility to Up-Regulation` (`mesh:D015854`). The gene,

represented by `ncit:C16612`, is linked to `Disease Specificity` (`sio:SIO_001351`), `Disease Pleiotropy` (`sio:SIO_001352`), and a Lung-CABO-specific class for `Loss-of-Function Intolerance Probability`.

Additional relations exist with `Pathway` (`CABO:Pathway`), `Cell` (`ncit:C12508`), and `Protein` (`ncit:C17021`), which belongs to `obo:PR_000000001`.

C. Disease-Variant Association

This association is represented by `sio:SIO_000897` and quantified through `Score` (`ncit:C25338`). The variant, represented by `OBO:SO_0001060`, includes attributes such as `Alternative Allele` (`geno:GENO_0000476`), `Reference Allele` (`geno:GENO_0000152`), and `chromosomal positioning` (`sio:SIO_000792`, `sio:SIO_000791`, `sio:SIO_000899`).

D. Disease-Chemical Association

This association is represented by `sio:SIO_000993` was defined to identify the connections between certain chemicals and lung cancer. In Lung-CABO it was conceived to serve as a link to a new module aimed at integrating and analyzing the relationship between the chemicals involved in the disease and the potential exposure of individuals.

In Figure 1, associations are shown in blue, while related entities appear in orange. The total number of nodes and edges in the Lung-CABO knowledge graph is summarized in **Table I**. These values reflect the current scale of integrated entities and associations derived from various biological data sources.

TABLE I
TOTAL NUMBER OF NODES AND EDGES IN THE LUNG-CABO
KNOWLEDGE GRAPH.

Element	Total
Nodes	37,989,712
Edges	226,300,688

V. ONTOLOGY EVALUATION

To ensure the quality, consistency, and correctness of the Lung-CABO ontology, a rigorous validation process was conducted. This evaluation comprised two main steps: (i) identifying potential modeling pitfalls and inconsistencies and (ii) verifying compliance with the ontology’s requirements through unit tests with SPARQL queries. The ontology was analyzed using the Ontology Pitfall Scanner! (OOPS!) [36], which detected common pitfalls typically found in ontology design. The identified issues included: (i) P04: Creation of unconnected ontology elements, (ii) P08: Missing annotations, (iii) P11: Missing domain or range in properties, (iv) P13: Inverse relationships not explicitly declared and (v) P22: Use of different naming conventions within the ontology. All pitfalls associated with newly implemented entities were addressed and resolved before proceeding with further validation.

Additionally, logical consistency was verified using the HermiT and Pellet reasoners within Protégè. Both reasoning engines confirmed the absence of inconsistencies, ensuring the coherence and correctness of the ontology’s axioms and relationships. To confirm that the ontology met the defined requirements and competency questions, a Knowledge Graph was generated, and a series of SPARQL unit tests were designed and executed. The validation process followed these steps:

- Mapping Rule Generation: the Mapeathor [38] tool was used to generate the mapping rules, selecting YARRML as the mapping language.
- Materialization of the Knowledge Graph: the mapping rules were processed using Morph-KGC [39], transforming the structured data into RDF triples and generating Turtle (TTL) files.

- Data storage: the TTL files were loaded into a Virtuoso triplestore, deployed via a Docker image to facilitate efficient query execution.
- Execution of SPARQL Unit Tests: a set of SPARQL queries was executed over the Virtuoso triplestore to verify:
 - The correctness of the conceptual model of the ontology.
 - The existence and validity of defined relationships.
 - The proper classification of entities according to the ontology structure.
 - The successful execution of these SPARQL unit tests confirmed that the ontology accurately represents domain knowledge and complies with the specified requirements.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

This article presents Lung-CABO, an ontology designed to model the association of biological concepts in lung cancer. Lung-CABO provides a reusable and scalable framework, allowing for expansion both in terms of data and ontological structure. In particular, the class representing associations with chemical compounds serves as a key linking point for integrating information on environmental risk factors. Unlike other ontologies, Lung-CABO focuses specifically on lung cancer and its subtypes, integrating data from relevant databases on the disease. This integration enables more precise and comprehensive analyses, facilitating a deeper understanding of the biological factors involved. For future work, the ontology will be expanded by incorporating environmental information relevant to lung cancer through the development of a new module. In this context, the association class between chemical compounds and disease will act as a bridge between the two modules. Additionally, Lung-CABO will be explored as input for artificial intelligence models, aiming to identify and discover new risk factors associated with lung cancer.

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